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Abstract. this article deals with theoretical background of the evolving speaking skills. In addition, author gives several notions from prominent pedagogs who contributed in this sphere.

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In the pedagogical literature, the process of learning a foreign language is denoted by different terms: perception, representation, concept, skill, skill, mental action, etc. Since the learning process is primarily related to psychology, it seems advisable to look for an answer to the question in this branch of pedagogical knowledge: how best to organize the teaching of foreign language at school.

The mechanism of speech perception in the native language in some cases may completely coincide with the mechanisms of formation of foreign language speech. We mean those cases when students learn new concepts for them based on the means of a foreign language. Direct connections between concepts and words of a foreign language can sometimes be formed when mastering simple linguistic phenomena based on audiovisual means (subject actions, films, etc.). However, in most cases, students perceive foreign-language units through the prism of their native language. "...Experience has shown, - writes L. V. Shcherba, - that it is possible to expel the native language from the learning process (and thus combine this process without giving the foreign language any weapon for self-defense against the influence of the native), but that it is impossible to expel the native language from the heads of students in school conditions; students, after all the explanations of the teacher, who seeks to explain the meaning of this or that according to the rules of the methodist methodology another word or linguistic phenomenon without the help of the native language, however, only fully understand this meaning when they find an equivalent for it in their native language" [1].

So, primary skills include three main points:

- a) the formation of an elementary (diffuse, generalized) association;
- b) subsequent elementary analysis;
- c) improvement through analysis and synthesis. This is a detailed cycle that is most often found when working on written texts. However, in a number of cases, especially in the oral perception of speech material, there may be a loss of the middle link - analysis.

The first and third stages, instantly combining, form a single synthetic stage of listening to foreign language speech.

The characterized primary skills determine the final result of learning at the first level. The achievement of this goal occurs in the process of performing a series of practical actions in accordance with the patterns of speech communication.

Language actions (selection and construction, analogy and opposition) are used in teaching listening and reading foreign language speech both in extralinguistic and linguistic situations.

From a methodological point of view, it is very important not to allow the identification of the concepts of "oral speech" and "spoken language".

Colloquial speech represents the functioning of a language in a certain sphere of its application and correlates with such functional and stylistic varieties of speech as official business, scientific, journalistic, and artistic. Oral speech is a form of communication and,

from the point of view of functional and stylistic, it can be official-business, scientific, colloquial, etc. [2]. It follows that the subject of education at school should not just be "oral speech", but spoken, more precisely literary-colloquial speech in its oral form. However, oral speech, which is taught in secondary schools and sometimes in special universities, is far from natural spoken language. This is, as a rule, bookish speech in oral form, devoid of the features required for German colloquial speech and having an "ascetic" character [3].

In order to solve methodological issues related to the teaching of spoken language and to develop a certain system of exercises, it is absolutely necessary to clearly understand what spoken language is in linguistic and stylistic terms, in what ratio are stylistically neutral and stylistically colored language material, what is the sequence of their passage, which language means must be studied by students, which are optional and which ones can be omitted.

English colloquial speech as one of the functionally stylistic varieties of speech is characterized by special stylistic features (emotionality, ease, brevity, etc.), which are at the same time norms for the construction of any colloquial utterance and are realized as a result of a certain selection, combination and application of commonly used means, as well as with the help of phonetic, lexical and grammatical means functioning exclusively in colloquial speech. According to this, the teacher must teach students a minimum of linguistic means that characterize spoken language.

List of used literature

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